

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The Best Proximity Point Problem for New Types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ - Contraction with Application

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Abstract

Objectives: To generate the best proximity point theorem for new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ - contraction. **Methods:** By using generalized $\alpha - \beta$ - proximal quasi contraction and Ciric type G-contraction. **Findings:** We made new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ - contraction. **Novelty/Improvement:** we give new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ - contraction which is a generalization of generalized $\alpha - \beta$ - proximal quasi contraction and Ciric type G-contraction.

Keywords: New types of Ciric α - β -contraction; Best proximity point; Ciric type G-contraction; generalized α - β - proximal quasi contraction; Cauchy Sequence

1 Introduction

The Banach-contraction principal on complete metric spaces was introduced in 1922. Every self mapping T on complete metric space (X, d) satisfying $d(Tx, Ty) \leq kd(x, y)$, for all $x, y \in X$, where $k \in (0, 1)$, has a unique fixed point in X. This result has been extended and generalized by many authors in different ways⁽¹⁻³⁾. Some other extensions of Banach contraction principle have been presented by considering the concept of best proximity point. A point x in A for which $d(x, Tx) = d(A, B)$ is called a best proximity point of T, whenever a non-self mapping T has no fixed point. A best proximity point represent optimal approximate solution to the equation $Tx = x$.

The first result on cyclic contraction and best proximity point was reported by Kirk et. al.⁽⁴⁾. Their results are the generalization of the usual contraction and fixed point. Eldered and Veeramani⁽⁵⁾ proved the existence of a best proximity point for proximal pointwise contraction maps. Anuradha and Veeramani⁽⁶⁾ proved the existence of a best proximity point for proximal pointwise contraction. Recently many authors have studied and generalize various concept related to the best proximity points⁽⁷⁻¹⁴⁾.

The main objective of this paper is to generalized the result of Mohammad Ladh. Ayari⁽¹⁵⁾ introduced new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ -contractive mapping on metric spaces involving β comparison function and Ciric type G-contraction.

In this paper to prove the existence of best proximity problem for new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ - contraction on metric spaces endowed with binary relations.

Considering a pair (A, B) of non-empty subset of (X, d) , we will use the following notations in this paper:
 $(A, B) = \text{inf} \{d(x, y) : x \in A, y \in B\}$;

$$A_0 = \{x \in A : d(x, y) = d(A, B) \text{ for some } y \in B\};$$

$$B_0 = \{y \in B : d(x, y) = d(A, B) \text{ for some } x \in A\}.$$

Definition 1.1. ⁽¹⁶⁾ Let (A, B) be a pair of non-empty subsets of a metric space (X, d) such that A_0 is non-empty. Then the pair (A, B) is said to have the P-property iff $d(x_1, y_1) = d(x_2, y_2) = d(A, B) \Rightarrow d(x_1, x_2) = d(y_1, y_2)$ for all $x_1, x_2 \in A_0$ and $y_1, y_2 \in B_0$.

Definition 1.2. ⁽¹⁷⁾ Let $\beta \in (0, \infty)$. A β -comparison function is a map $\phi : (0, +\infty) \rightarrow (0, +\infty)$ fulfilling the following properties:

- (1) ϕ is non-decreasing;
- (2) $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \phi_\beta^n(t) = 0$ for all $t > 0$, where ϕ_β^n denotes the n^{th} iterate of ϕ_β and $\phi_\beta(t) = \phi(\beta.t)$;
- (3) there exist $s \in (0, \infty)$ such that $\sum_{n=1}^\infty \phi_\beta^n(s) < \infty$.

The set of all β comparison functions ϕ satisfying (1)-(3) will be denoted by ϕ_β .

Definition 1.3. ⁽¹⁸⁾ Let $T : A \rightarrow B$ and $\alpha : A \times A \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$. We say that T is α -proximal admissible if $\alpha(x_1, x_2) \geq 1$ and $d(u_1, Tx_1) = d(u_2, Tx_2) = d(A, B)$, then $\alpha(u_1, u_2) \geq 1$, for all $x_1, x_2, u_1, u_2 \in A$.

Definition 1.4. ⁽¹⁸⁾ A non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ is said to be (α, d) regular, where $\alpha : A \times A \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$, if for all (x, y) such that $0 \leq \alpha(x, y) < 1$, there exists $u_0 \in A_0$ such that $\alpha(x, u_0) \geq 1$ and $\alpha(y, u_0) \geq 1$.

In an arbitrary graph G, a link is an edge of G with distinct ends and a loop is an edge of G with identical ends. Two or more links of G with the same pairs of ends are called parallel edges of G.

Let (X, d) be a metric space and G be a directed graph with vertex set $V(G) = X$ such that the edge set $E(G)$ contains all loops, that is $(x, x) \in E(G)$ for all $x \in X$. Assume further that G has no parallel edges. Under these hypothesis, the graph G can be easily denoted by the ordered pair $(V(G), E(G))$ and it is said that the metric space (X, d) is endowed with the graph G.

Definition 1.5. ⁽¹⁹⁾ A non self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ is G-proximal if T satisfies

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (y_1, y_2) \in E(G) \\ d(x_1, Ty_1) = d(A, B) \\ d(x_2, Ty_2) = d(A, B) \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow (x_1, x_2) \in E(G),$$

for all $x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in A$.

Definition 1.6. ⁽²⁰⁾ A non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ is a Ciric type G-contraction, if there exists $\alpha \in [0, 1)$ such that $d(Tx, Ty) \leq \alpha.Q_T(x, y)$, for all $x, y \in A$ with $(x, y) \in E(G)$, where

$$Q_T(x, y) = \max \left\{ d(x, y), d(x, Tx) - d(A, B), d(y, Ty) - d(A, B), \frac{d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)}{2} - d(A, B) \right\}.$$

Definition 1.7. ⁽¹⁵⁾ A non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ is said to be a generalized $\alpha - \beta$ -proximal quasi-contractive, where $\alpha : A \times A \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ iff there exist $\phi \in \phi_\beta$ and positive numbers $\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_4$ such that

$$\alpha(x, y)d(Tx, Ty) \leq \phi(M_T(x, y)), \quad \forall x, y \in A,$$

Where

$$M_T(x, y) = \max \{ \alpha_0 d(x, y), \alpha_1 [d(x, Tx) - d(A, B)], \alpha_2 [d(y, Ty) - d(A, B)], \alpha_3 [d(y, Tx) - d(A, B)], \alpha_4 [d(x, Ty) - d(A, B)] \}.$$

To prove our main results, we need the following lemma:

Lemma 1.8. ⁽¹⁵⁾ Let $T : A \rightarrow B$ be a non-self-mapping and $\alpha : A \times A \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$, satisfying the following conditions:

- (1) $T(A_0) \subset B_0$;
- (2) T is α -proximal admissible;
- (3) There exist elements $x_0, x_1 \in A_0$ such that $d(x_1, Tx_0) = d(A, B)$ and $\alpha(x_0, x_1) \geq 1$.

Then there exists a sequence $\{x_n\} \subset A_0$ such that $d(x_{n+1}, Tx_n) = d(A, B)$ and $\alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) \geq 1$, such a sequence $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

2 Results and Discussion

Definition 2.1. We introduced a new type of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ -contraction. A non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ is a new type of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ -contraction where $\alpha : A \times A \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ if there exist $\phi \in \phi_\beta$ and positive numbers $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ such that,

$\alpha(x, y) \cdot d(Tx, Ty) \leq \varphi(M_T(x, y)), \forall x, y \in A,$
 where

$$M_T(x, y) = \max\{\alpha_0 d(x, y), \alpha_1 d(x, Tx) - d(A, B), \alpha_2 d(y, Ty) - d(A, B), \alpha_3 [\frac{d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)}{2} - d(A, B)]\}.$$

Example : Let $X = R^2$ with metric

$$d((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2)) = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2}$$

and put $A = \{(x, 1) : x \in [0, 1]\}$ and $B = \{(y, 0) : y \in [0, 1]\}$, and $T : A \rightarrow B$ is defined by

$$T(x, 1) = \begin{cases} (0, 0), & \text{if } 0 \leq x < 1 \\ (\frac{1}{3}, 0), & \text{if } x = 1. \end{cases}$$

Then it is easy to see that $d(A, B) = 1$ and $A_0 = A$ and $B_0 = B$. So that T is a new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ contraction with $\varphi(t) = t, \alpha \in [0, 1]$ and $\alpha_i = \frac{1}{3^{i+1}}$ for $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

Theorem 2.2. Let A and B be non-empty closed subsets of a complete metric space (X, d) such that A_0 is non-empty. Let $\alpha : A \times A \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ and $\varphi \in \varphi_\beta$. Assume that non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ satisfying the following conditions:

- (1) $T(A_0) \subset B_0$ and the pair (A, B) satisfies the P-property;
- (2) T is α proximal admissible;
- (3) There exist elements $x_0, x_1 \in A_0$ such that $d(x_1, Tx_0) = d(A, B)$ and $\alpha(x_0, x_1) \geq 1$;
- (4) T is continuous on new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ contraction;
- (5) if $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in A such that $\alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) \geq 1$ and $\{x_{n(k)}\}$ of $\{x_n\}$ such that $\alpha(x_{n(k)}, x^*) \geq 1$ for all k ;
- (6) there exist $\alpha - \beta$ contraction;
- (7) φ is continuous, $\beta > \max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\}$.

Then T has a best proximity point $x^* \in A$ such that $d(x^*, Tx^*) = d(A, B)$.

Proof. From given to condition (3), there exist $x_0, x_1 \in A$ such that, $d(x_1, Tx_0) = d(A, B)$ and $\alpha(x_0, x_1) \geq 1$. Since $T(A_0) \subset B_0$, there exist $x_2 \in A_0$ such that $d(x_2, Tx_1) = d(A, B)$. Since T is α proximal admissible and using $\alpha(x_0, x_1) \geq 1, d(x_1, Tx_0) = d(x_2, Tx_1) = d(A, B)$. This implies that $\alpha(x_1, x_2) \geq 1$.

In a similar condition, by induction sequence $\{x_n\} \subset A_0$ such that

$$d(x_{n+1}, Tx_n) = d(A, B), \tag{1}$$

and $\alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in N \cup \{0\}$.

Using the P-property we deduce that

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) = d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n), \forall n \in N \tag{2}$$

Since T is new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ contractive, there exist a function $\varphi \in \varphi_\beta$ such that

$$\alpha(x_{n-1}, x_n) \cdot d(Tx_{n-1}, Tx_n) \leq \varphi(M_T(x_{n-1}, x_n)), \quad \forall n \in N \tag{3}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} M_T(x_{n-1}, x_n) &= \max\{\alpha_0 d(x_{n-1}, x_n), \alpha_1 [d(x_{n-1}, Tx_{n-1}) - d(A, B)], \alpha_2 [d(x_n, Tx_n) - d(A, B)] \\ &\quad \alpha_3 [\frac{d(x_{n-1}, Tx_n) + d(x_n, Tx_{n-1})}{2} - d(A, B)]\} \\ &= \max\{\alpha_0 d(x_{n-1}, x_n), \alpha_1 [d(x_{n-1}, Tx_{n-1}) - d(A, B)], \alpha_2 [d(x_n, Tx_n) - d(A, B)], \\ &\quad \alpha_3 [\frac{d(x_{n-1}, Tx_n) - d(A, B)}{2} + \alpha_3 \frac{d(x_n, Tx_{n-1}) - d(A, B)}{2}]\} \\ &= \max\{\alpha_0 d(x_{n-1}, x_n), \alpha_1 [d(x_{n-1}, Tx_{n-1}) - d(A, B)], \alpha_2 [d(x_n, Tx_n) - d(A, B)], \\ &\quad \alpha_3 [\frac{d(x_{n-1}, Tx_n) - d(A, B)}{2}]\} \\ &\leq \max\{\alpha_0 d(x_{n-1}, x_n), \alpha_1 d(x_{n-1}, x_n), \alpha_2 d(x_n, x_{n+1}), \alpha_3 [\frac{d(x_{n-1}, x_n) d(x_n, x_{n+1})}{2}]\} \end{aligned}$$

$$M_T(x_{n-1}, x_n) \leq \beta \max\{d(x_{n-1}, x_n), d(x_n, x_{n+1})\}, \tag{4}$$

where φ is non-decreasing, then we get that

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{n+1}, x_n) &\leq \varphi(\beta \max\{d(x_{n-1}, x_n), d(x_n, x_{n+1})\}) \\ &= \varphi_\beta(\max\{d(x_{n-1}, x_n), d(x_n, x_{n+1})\}), \end{aligned}$$

Suppose that, for some n , we have

$$d(x_{n-1}, x_n) \leq d(x_n, x_{n+1}),$$

then we get

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \varphi_\beta d(x_n, x_{n+1})$$

$< d(x_n, x_{n+1})$,
 which is contradiction.
 Therefore, for all $n \geq 0$,

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \varphi_\beta d(x_{n-1}, x_n), \forall n \in N. \tag{5}$$

Now, by induction, we find

$$d(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \varphi_\beta^n(d(x_0, x_1)), \forall n \in N \cup \{0\}. \tag{6}$$

Now we will show that $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

Consider $m, n \in N$ with $m > n$, using the triangle inequality and the above inequality (6), we get

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_n, x_m) &\leq \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} d(x_k, x_{k+1}) \\ &\leq \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} \varphi_\beta^k d(x_0, x_1) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n, m \rightarrow +\infty. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $A_0 \subset A$ and Since (X, d) is complete, there exist $x^* \in A$ (depending on x_0 and x_1) such that $x_n \rightarrow x^* \in A$.

We next to show that x^* is best proximity point for T .

Using hypothesis (5) of the theorem, \exists a subsequence $\{x_{n(k)}\}$ to $\{x_n\}$ such that $\alpha(x_{n(k)}, x^*) \geq 1 \forall k$.

Since T is new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ contractive, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tx_{n(k)}, Tx^*) &\leq \alpha(x_{n(k)}, x^*)d(Tx_{n(k)}, Tx^*) \\ &\leq \varphi(M_T(x_{n(k)}, x^*)), \forall k \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where

$$M_T(x_{n(k)}, x^*) = \max\{\alpha_0 d(x_{n(k)}, x^*), \alpha_1 d(x_{n(k)}, Tx_{n(k)}) - d(A, B), \alpha_2 [d(x^*, Tx^*) - d(A, B)],$$

$$\alpha_3 \left[\frac{d(x_{n(k)}, Tx^*) + d(x^*, Tx_{n(k)})}{2} \right] - d(A, B)\}. \tag{8}$$

Using triangular inequality, We have

$$\begin{aligned} d(x^*, Tx^*) &\leq d(x^*, x_{n(k)+1}) + d(x_{n(k)+1}, Tx_{n(k)}) + d(Tx_{n(k)}, Tx^*) \\ &= d(x^*, x_{n(k)+1}) + d(A, B) + d(Tx_{n(k)}, Tx^*) \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$d(x^*, Tx^*) - d(x^*, x_{n(k)+1}) - d(A, B) \leq d(Tx_{n(k)}, Tx^*), \forall k.$$

Using (7) and (9), we get

$$d(x^*, Tx^*) - d(x^*, x_{n(k)+1}) - d(A, B) \leq \varphi(M_T(x_{n(k)}, x^*)) \tag{10}$$

$$\leq \varphi(\max\{\alpha_0 d(x_{n(k)}, x^*), \alpha_1 [d(x_{n(k)}, Tx_{n(k)}) - d(A, B)]\},$$

$$\alpha_2 [d(x^*, Tx^*) - d(A, B)], \alpha_3 [\frac{d(x_{n(k)}, Tx^*) + d(x^*, Tx_{n(k)})}{2} - d(A, B)]\}.$$

Assume $\rho = d(x^*, Tx^*) - d(A, B) > 0$. Let us we consider two separate cases as follows. If φ is continuous, as $k \rightarrow \infty$, we get

$$\rho \leq \varphi(\max\{\alpha_0 d(x_{n(k)}, x^*), \alpha_1 [d(x_{n(k)}, x_{n(k)+1}) + d(x_{n(k)+1}, Tx_{n(k)})] - d(A, B),$$

$$\alpha_2 [d(x^*, Tx^*) - d(A, B)], \alpha_3 [\frac{d(x_{n(k)}, Tx^*) - d(A, B)}{2} + \frac{d(x^*, Tx_{n(k)}) - d(A, B)}{2}]\})$$

$$\rho \leq \varphi(\max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\} \rho) \leq \varphi(\beta \rho) < \rho,$$

which is contradiction.

If $\beta > \max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\}$ and we claim also that $\rho = 0$. Suppose by contradiction that $\rho > 0$, letting $k \rightarrow \infty$ in (8), we get

$$M_T(x_{n(k)}, x^*) \rightarrow \max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\} \rho.$$

If there exist $\varepsilon > 0$ and $N > 0$, such that for all $n > N$, we have

$$M_T(x_{n(k)}, x^*) < (\max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\} + \varepsilon) \rho \tag{11}$$

and

$$\beta > (\max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\} + \varepsilon),$$

therefore in equation (10) and (11)

$$d(x^*, Tx^*) - d(x^*, x_{n(k)+1}) - d(A, B) \leq \varphi(M_T(x_{n(k)}, x^*))$$

$$< \varphi((\max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\} + \varepsilon) \rho)$$

$$< \varphi_\beta(\frac{\max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\} + \varepsilon}{\beta} \rho)$$

$$< \frac{\max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\} + \varepsilon}{\beta} \rho$$

$$< \rho.$$

Consequently, by letting $k \rightarrow \infty$, we get

$$\rho < \frac{\max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\} + \varepsilon}{\beta} \rho < \rho,$$

which is contradiction as well.

Hence our claim holds.

Thus, we proved that x^* is a best proximity point of T, that is $d(x^*, Tx^*) = d(A, B)$.

3 Application

Best proximity point for metric spaces endowed with a binary relation.

Before apply our results, we need some preliminaries. Let (X, d) be a metric space and R be a binary relation over X.

The symmetric relation attached to R.

$$x, y \text{ in } X, xRy \Leftrightarrow xRy \text{ or } yRx, \text{ Where } S = R \cup R^{-1}.$$

Definition 3.1. ⁽⁶⁾ Let X be a non-empty set. A non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ is called β -quasi-contractive if there exist $\beta > 0$ and $\varphi \in \varphi_\beta$ such that

$$x, y \in A : xRy \Rightarrow d(Tx, Ty) \leq \varphi(M_T(x, y))$$

$$\text{where } M_T(x, y) = \max\left\{\alpha_0 d(x, y), \alpha_1 d(x, Tx) - d(A, B), \alpha_2 d(y, Ty) - d(A, B), \alpha_3 \left[\frac{d(x, Ty) + d(y, Tx)}{2} - d(A, B)\right]\right\},$$

with $\alpha_k \geq 0$ for $k = 0, 1, 2, 3$.

Definition 3.2. ⁽¹⁴⁾ A non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ is a proximal comparative mapping if xRy and $d(u_1, Tx) = d(u_2, Ty) = d(A, B)$, $\forall x, y, u_1, u_2 \in A$ then u_1Ru_2 .

Theorem 3.3. Let A and B be non-empty closed subsets of a complete metric space (X, d) such that A_0 is non-empty. Let R be a binary relation over X. Assume that non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ satisfying the following conditions:

- (1) $T(A_0) \subset B_0$ and the pair (A, B) satisfies the P-property;
- (2) T is a proximal comparative mapping;
- (3) There exist elements $x_0, x_1 \in A_0$ such that $d(x_1, Tx_0) = d(A, B)$ and $\alpha(x_0, x_1) \geq 1$;
- (4) T is continuous on new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ contraction;

(5) if $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in A such that $\alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) \geq 1$ and $\{x_{n(k)}\}$ of $\{x_n\}$ such that $\alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $k(A, d, R)$ is regular;

(6) there exist $\alpha - \beta$ contractive;

(7) φ is continuous, $\beta > \max\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\}$,

then T has a best proximity point $x^* \in A$ such that $d(x^*, Tx^*) = d(A, B)$.

Proof. define the $\alpha : A \times A \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by:

$$\alpha(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } xRy \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

then T is α -admissible.

Assume that $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$, and $d(u_1, Tx) = d(u_2, Ty) = d(A, B)$ for some $x, y, u_1, u_2 \in A$. By the definition of α , we get xSy , $d(u_1, Tx) = d(u_2, Ty) = d(A, B)$.

Assertion (2) of the theorem implies that u_1Ru_2 , which gives us $\alpha(u_1, u_2) \geq 1$.

Assertion (3) if T is α -admissible and $d(x_1, Tx_0) = d(A, B)$.

Assertion (4) T is β -quasi-contractive means that T is new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ -contractive.

Also the condition (5) hold.

Next in condition (6) A is R -directed implies that the non-self mapping $T : A \rightarrow B$ is (α, d) is regular.

Now all the condition of theorem 2.2 are satisfied, which implies the existence of best proximity point for the non-self mapping T .

4 Conclusion

This study adds an improvement to the best proximity point theorems^(15,20), for Ciric type G -contraction and generalized $\alpha - \beta$ -proximal quasi contractive mappings. This improvement is obtained by introducing new types of Ciric $\alpha - \beta$ contraction involving Ciric type G -contraction by the generalization of the generalized $\alpha - \beta$ -proximal-quasi-contractive mappings on metric space. We have established application of best proximity point result for the case of non-self mappings on metric spaces endowed with binary operation.

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